

DETERMINATION OF FIELD BOUNDARY PARAMETERS IN DRILLING AND BLASTING PROCESSES IN OPEN PIT MINES

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Abstract. This article is from examples adapted to geological and geotechnological modeling in mining enterprises operating and drilling costs and the results of using several methods to increase productivity in some mining operations and drilling-blasting processes. The main goals and objectives of this article will be to reduce the number of drilling and blasting holes in mines and increase the blasting area. The cost of these objectives from an economic point of view is, firstly, directly proportional to the number of boreholes, and secondly, the associated increase in the extent of the blasting area. In the mines indicates an indirect effect on the recovery efficiency of the target material associated with excavation and blast damage. Therefore, drill strings, detonators, and detonators in the mine will be more about the problem of the boundary of the blasting area and create conditions for less drilling. During blasting and drilling processes in mining enterprises the main problem in creating an accurate surface model is that the mass of the cover rock is usually relative to the mass of the blasted area will be widely spaced. Coarse samples are obtained by drilling blast holes. So interpolation sufficiently exceed local variations in the underlying geology. Created in a mine borehole measurement reliable determination of geological boundaries in the field in real time data, we posed a local model estimation problem in an adaptive sampling system. The selection strategy based on the proposed information will consist of two stages. First, blast holes in mines are selected in a way that is adapted to the geology of the drilling and to obtain the maximum benefit in terms of their location. Mine blasting processes will consist of a step-by-step improvement of the spatial model. The second stage drilling-blasting processes in the mine depend on the forecast conducts expert-guided drilling at predetermined distances from geology and geology and in order to optimize the explosion, it is necessary to reduce its limit in order to reduce its damage.

Keywords: Open pit blasting processes, geological and geotechnical requirements, boreholes, charging of explosives in the mine, explosion limit, detonators in mines, field explosion limit, drilling area, field explosion sequence, mine technical parameters.

ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ГРАНИЧНЫХ ПАРАМЕТРОВ МЕСТОРОЖДЕНИЯ ПРИ ПРОВЕДЕНИИ БУРОВЗРЫВНЫХ РАБОТ В КАРЬЕРАХ ОТКРЫТЫМ СПОСОБОМ

Аннотация. В этой статье приведены примеры, адаптированные к геологическому и геотехнологическому моделированию эксплуатационных расходов горнодобывающих предприятий и затрат на бурение, а также результаты использования нескольких методов для повышения производительности некоторых горных работ и буровзрывных

процессов. Основными целями и задачами этой статьи будут сокращение количества буровых и взрывных скважин в шахтах и увеличение площади взрывных работ. Стоимость этих задач с экономической точки зрения, во-первых, прямо пропорциональна количеству скважин, а во-вторых, связанному с этим увеличению площади взрывных работ. В шахтах указывает на косвенное влияние на эффективность извлечения целевого материала, связанное с выемкой грунта и повреждениями от взрыва. Следовательно, бурильные колонны, детонаторы и взрыватели-детонаторы в шахте будут в большей степени решать проблему границы зоны взрывных работ и создавать условия для меньшего объема бурения. Во время процессов взрывных работ и бурения на горнодобывающих предприятиях основная проблема при создании точной модели поверхности заключается в том, что масса покровной породы обычно относительно массы взрывающей зоны будет сильно разнесена. Крупнозернистые образцы получают путем бурения взрывных скважин. Таким образом, интерполяция в достаточной степени превосходит локальные вариации в лежащей в основе геологии. Создав при измерении в шахтной скважине надежное определение геологических границ на месторождении по данным в режиме реального времени, мы поставили задачу оценки локальной модели в адаптивной системе отбора проб. Стратегия отбора, основанная на предложенной информации, будет состоять из двух этапов. Во-первых, взрывные скважины в шахтах выбираются таким образом, чтобы адаптироваться к геологии бурения и получить максимальную выгоду с точки зрения их расположения. Процессы взрывных работ на шахтах будут заключаться в поэтапном совершенствовании пространственной модели. Вторая стадия буровзрывных процессов в шахте зависит от прогноза, проводимого под руководством эксперта бурения на заранее определенных расстояниях от геологических объектов, и для оптимизации взрыва необходимо снизить его предел, чтобы уменьшить его ущерб.

Ключевые слова: Процессы взрывных работ открытым способом, геологические и геотехнические требования, скважины, загрузка взрывчатых веществ в шахту, предел взрываемости, детонаторы в шахтах, предел взрываемости на месторождении, площадь бурения, последовательность взрывов на месторождении, технические параметры шахты.

Introduction

The use of the most common processing operations in drilling-blasting processes in mines is gaining importance. Some countries have drilling processes accounts for nearly 40% of all blasting and drilling operations. Nevertheless, drilling processes and blasting in mining enterprises process management capabilities are of great importance in the mine. In the mine which may have a positive effect on the performance of the drilling process differs in overall processing quality, productivity and price. An examination of the drilling shows that the drilling depth increases.

Breakage of the tool during drilling processes in mines leads to production and processing costs. All these consequences are, of course, very undesirable from any production point of view. Mining drilling and blasting processes engineering components, various metal cutting operations such as milling and drilling are widely used. To carry out drilling and blasting processes in the mine to understand the behavior of the process, different answers are needed measured and controlled. In mining enterprises, blasting refers to the drilling of technological wells by means of

drilling equipment refers to rock and small pieces of rock formed by the impact of drilling bring up. The efficiency of drilling wells depends on many factors, the main of which is the drilling ability and fracture of the rocks. Rock drilling - the property of deformation under the influence of a tool. With the drilling ability of the rocks, the technological parameters of the drilling rigs are selected accordingly. Mining is the process of preparing ore for extraction by changing the natural state of the rock. Includes a focused process to ensure its effectiveness. Hard rock in preparation for rock blasting, and rocks of moderate hardness are mechanically broken. Grinding by mechanical method for crushing by blast method is more useful due to its high productivity, low cost and practical safety are high. In mining enterprises, until recently, open pits were mainly filled with flat shafts. In blasting processes in such a structure, there is a large formation on top of the rock mass where the detonators are charged.

Detonator stage during blasting with excessive crushing of mined rock near the charge problems were observed. In this case, when the charge explodes, there is a very large volume next to it. Fine crushed rocks are formed. Such unevenness of the open pit after the explosion, the rocks cause problems in working with them. Detonators in the mine the density of the explosion pressure is significantly reduced, preventing the processes of extreme fragmentation of the rock around the charge and due to overcrushing rocks, the time of the explosion actively affecting the mine rock mass. The charge of voltage waves created by the explosion of the expanded, lower and upper parts interference is observed. In this case, the air gap acts as the beginning of the explosion and a compensator that reduces the pressure generated during the charging chamber due to such a change the indicators of the explosion pulse are extremes of the surrounding rocks decreases, that is, the energy released in the explosion has the same effect on the ore mass of the mine. This conclusion is based on experiments carried out in various geological conditions approved. Thus, when the detonator charges explode, the air is divided into a space, as a result intersection of voltage waves generated by the top and bottom of the charge, field of mine in the array, the drilling-blasting level can be good and uniform. In this case, in mining enterprises, the area to be blasted is prepared by the drilling area before starting the block, and the border of the blasting area after calculations are made, detonator charging operations and detonation area limits are ordered then the charging sequence is performed. An engineer-technical worker carries out blasting works in the area of the blasting limit area in the mines.

The beginning of each shift is prepared by drilling workers and drivers of charging machines. The limit of the blasting area is in the mines, depending on the parameters of the mine a number of generated wells in the block and prepare them for blasting and introduce all blasting instructions documents are reviewed for safe implementation. Explosives detonation block brought under the supervision of the charging machine by the mine engineer or blasting officer and charging is done. The route of movement of the loader is mine engineer or shall be shown by the blasting officer.

After the charger is transferred to the charger technical parameters of the mine, the boundary of the mine field prepares it for charging. In this case, the blasting officer is a charging machine and when lowering the hoses into the well, it reports that the drive of the mixing chamber has been activated. In the mine the mass of the explosive is controlled to determine the dimensions of the blast area. After the wells are charged to a certain height, they during blasting operations,

the worker lowers the explosive into the well. After the charging machine runs out of explosives the charging unit of the warhead detonator allows it to leave.

Picture1. Determining the layout of detonators in the mine field in accordance with the parameters of the technical indicators of the open mine during the drilling and blasting processes in the open mine.

Drilling and blasting operations in mining exploration widely used in the process of soldering, rarely explosive materials are used in mountainous terrain, in the construction of overland transport routes, in drilling for drilling operations, or for the extraction of underground minerals. it is also used in the construction of production sites. Do these things the main purpose of increasing the rocks of medium and above medium strength is to erode the rocks. The main purpose of drilling and blasting extraction and crushing of rocky rocks from the massif. Drilling

and blasting work is the erosion and crushing of rocky rocks during the passage of mine shafts a set of interrelated technological processes carried out for the purpose. Drilling and blasting consists of several sequential processes: spur Drilling (wells), placing explosive charges, (charging) and detonating charges, spurs and wells for placing explosives are designed artificially drilled cavities. The spur is up to 75 mm in diameter and an artificial cylindrical cavity in a rock mass up to 5 m deep, into a pit it is said. A well is a cylindrical well of any diameter, 5 m deep artificial, exceeding or exceeding 75 mm in diameter at any depth a cylindrical cavity, called a groove. Blasting is an explosive placing charges and detonating explosive charges is said to increase. Charging is the process of placing charges in the charging chamber called charging. Now it's spinning, spinning, spinning, spinning percussive, flame, rotary and mixed drilling methods are widely used. Circulation drill - rotary drill with a spindle up to 50 mm in diameter and 5 meters, it is used when the hardness of the rock is up to 7. Rotary drilling mainly used in coal, slanes and salt mines. Percussion drilling – percussive drilling is mainly carried out with drill hammers (perforators).

Conclusions

Based on the results, it was shown that mining enterprises should have each pre-separated blast hole and blast zone. The mine must be placed on a confined surface before drilling blast holes in the confined area. We think the conclusion is that the explosives were fired along with the blast holes that were pre-blasted and it was not doing well. The cracks in the mine are also mine the row found outside is placed along the pre-allocated line. The distance between the ratio of the mine blasting area to the drilled surface from the parameters of the pre-allocated mine boundary area section holes are set at average values of 1.5-1.8 m, optimal for a drilling diameter of 70 mm for a bench height of 15 m and 25 m. based mountain the results of the drilling process according to the results before the necessary division according to the formation of rocks a detonation vibration study confirmed that the reduction in vibration level was up to 20% due to presplit. These results also confirmed that the pre-separation works as a filter and that we can observe causing the vibration to decrease. An explosion in the border area of the mine detonating wires, cords, and a pre-separated detonation signal transmission will be required to open the holes. Pre-drilled holes gave better results than those worked with detonating cord. The pre-split blast results also confirmed the mouth of the pre-split holes. Rock blasting distances in a mine vary length and depth. Mine explosions are detonated by the electronic delay mass of rock detonators, as it helped to achieve the desired detonation results in the formation of geological cracks and the drilling-blasting process. better control over the delay intervals and the distance between the blasting round holes is created. The fractured rock mass near the cracks, the longer the cutting wire will be reinforced with bolts. This is planned design the fire of high benches in such a way that the minimum throw of the blasted area is carried out.

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